

ESTABLISHING LEARNER'S INNOVATIVE ACTIVITY ACCORDING TO AN INTEGRATIVE APPROACH

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Abstract. The article deals with some peculiarities of integration in pedagogy and integrated lesson in educational process. It also discusses the form of conducting integrated lessons, the use of various types of work, the results of integrated learning and its significance.

Key words: integration in pedagogy, education system, integrated lessons, integrated approach, students' interest in subjects.

The integrated approaching to the lesson is one of the innovations of the modern methodology. This technology boldly invades unshakable school curricula and links seemingly incompatible subjects. English is no exception. On the contrary, in essence, the school subject "English" is integrated. It is all permeated with interdisciplinary connections and offers students' knowledge of many areas of science, art, culture, as well as real everyday life. An integrated lesson, built on the synthesis of information from various educational subjects, stimulates the analytical activity of students, forms the ability to transfer knowledge from one industry to another, which contributes to the development of meta-subject and a systematic approach to teaching. Thanks to all of the above, a holistic perception of reality is achieved in teaching practice.

Integration is a relatively new approach in pedagogy, the introduction of which can raise the level of the educational process of the younger generation. Integration in pedagogy and education is, first of all, the interaction of various elements of any system in order to obtain something holistic, new. The concept of "system" in modern pedagogy can be used in different aspects, for example: an educational institution as a system; system of training classes; the system of relationships

between children and teachers, etc. Integration in pedagogy is traditionally considered in two aspects:

- 1) as a state characterized by consistency, orderliness and stability of connections between various elements;
- 2) as a process that leads to a given state.

Thus, integration in pedagogy is a very important indicator, indicating the effectiveness of the entire education system; it serves as a criterion for its integrity. The interaction of various elements in the educational process is a rather complex and multilevel process. In connection with these in pedagogy, there are various approaches to the definition of the concept of integration.

So, according to V.S. Bezrukova, integration is the highest form of interconnection, expressing the unity of all elements that make up the education system, and determining its content. Integration in pedagogy is a well-structured, multi-component and carefully organized connection of all elements of the education system, the ultimate goal of which is the student's self-development. All elements in the education system serve one goal - the versatile development of the child, they contribute to the satisfaction of their interests and abilities, ensure the coordination of influence on the motivational, emotional, efficient-practical and volitional spheres of the child's personality. Here are some peculiarities of integrated learning. [1,381]

Benefits of integration approach in the lesson

They perceive the world around students in diversity and unity, and often the subjects of the subject cycle, aimed at studying individual phenomena of this unity, do not give an idea of the whole phenomenon, splitting it into disparate fragments. Integrated lessons develop the potential of the students themselves, encourage active cognition of the surrounding reality, to comprehend and find causal relationships, to the development of logic, thinking, and communication skills. A greater extent than ordinary ones, they contribute to the development of speech, the formation of the ability to compare, generalize, and draw conclusions. The form of conducting

integrated lessons is non-standard and exciting. The use of various types of work maintains the attention of students at a high level, which allows us to talk about the developmental effectiveness of such lessons. They relieve fatigue, overstrain of students by switching to a variety of activities, sharply increase cognitive interest, and serve the development of imagination, attention, thinking, speech and memory of schoolchildren.

Integration provides an opportunity for self-realization, self-expression, creativity of the teacher, promote the disclosure of the abilities of his students. Integration is a source of finding new facts that confirm or deepen certain conclusions, students' observations in various subjects. Integrated lessons give the student a fairly broad and vivid idea of the world in which he lives, of mutual assistance, of the existence of a diverse world of material and artistic culture.

The results of integrated learning and its significance:

Contributes to the development of the scientific style of thinking of students; makes it possible for students to widely use the natural-scientific method of cognition forms an integrated approach to academic subjects.

A single view from the point of view of natural sciences on a particular problem, reflecting objective connections in the world; improves the quality of students' knowledge; increases and develops students' interest in subjects.

Forms the belief of students that they can learn more complex things with understanding in comparison with those offered in the textbook. You to use the author's computer programs of students (created on the basis of integration) in the further educational process.

Also expands the horizons of students, contributes to the development of creative abilities of students, helps a deeper understanding and assimilation of the program material of the main course of physics, mathematics, computer science at the level of application of knowledge, abilities, skills in new conditions; introduces students to scientific research activities.

Personal results in English: the formation of a person's civic identity, mainly in its general cultural component; the formation of goodwill, respect and tolerance towards other countries and peoples;

General idea of the world as a multilingual and multicultural community; awareness of language, including foreign language, as the main means of communication between people;

Acquaintance with the world of foreign peers using the means of the studied foreign language (through children's folklore, some samples of children's fiction, traditions, intercultural communication).

To summarizing all that has been said, we can say that the concept of "integration" in pedagogy means: a comprehensive description of the goals of education, a combination of pedagogical tools used both in educational and in extracurricular activities. Also, integrity in achieving planned results, the relationship of the main and additional education, flexibility of organizing educational activities using various methods and forms of extracurricular activities; the creation of creative circles, as well as the introduction of integrative courses, the interaction of all elements of the educational process.

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